

TEACHERS' EMOTIONAL BALANCE IN RELATION TO MANAGEMENT OF GRADE 1 LEARNERS' ANXIETY

DIANNE ROSE L. GORGONIO

Abstract.

The study aimed to determine the significant relationship between teachers' emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners' anxiety. This study was conducted with 30 elementary teachers in the Banaybanay District. The research revealed the exceptional emotional resilience of teachers and their effectiveness in supporting students with anxiety, in line with established literature highlighting the crucial role of teacher support in mitigating anxiety and boosting academic performance. The remarkably low standard deviations in emotional balance indicators underscore the consistency of teachers' emotional well-being, reinforcing the concept of a nurturing classroom environment. Although extensive mean scores suggest effective strategies for alleviating anxiety, the study identifies areas needing further enhancement, particularly in stress management and sharing experiences for anxiety control. The moderate correlation observed between emotional balance and anxiety management underscores the pivotal role of teachers' emotional health in addressing student anxiety. This research underscores the significant impact of emotional balance and adjustment on effective anxiety management, underscoring the importance of regulating teachers' emotions for a nurturing classroom atmosphere. Consequently, educational institutions were encouraged to prioritize strategies that promote teachers' emotional equilibrium through ongoing professional development, fostering a supportive environment for Grade 1 students' anxiety management.

KEY WORDS

1. Teachers' Emotional Balance.
2. Emotional Manifestation.
3. Emotional Self-Awareness, .

1. Introduction

Since the global shift to distance learning in response to the pandemic, early childhood education practitioners worldwide have shown remarkable resilience in grappling with new teaching routines that can feel harsh, limiting, and confining. This is not a localized issue, but a global phenomenon that has affected teachers in every corner of the world. In these challenging circumstances, teachers have had to adapt to new modes of instruction, significantly different from the traditional in-person teaching they are accustomed to. This transition has elicited a range of emotional responses, from those who have embraced the new normal to those still grappling with the changes. It is very important for the teachers to manage their emotional balance well, so, if possible, have one-to-one conversations with them to understand how they are feeling and to help ease their anxieties. It is also important to communicate with their par-

ents. Use pair work and group work, giving them roles that best use their strengths. As a global phenomenon, educators have undeniably resigned from their jobs because they could not make the necessary adjustments and believed that such an ordeal would be detrimental to their mental, emotional, and psychological well-being. This is not an isolated issue, but a worldwide crisis that demands immediate attention. As a result of this setup, teacher turnover poses a problem for schools as they implement learning continuity plans because preschool teachers, precisely their social and emotional skills, are critical in their young pupils' social and emotional development (Denham et al., 2012). The international community's education sectors face a common problem regarding teachers' job commitment, as several have left the school organization either temporarily or permanently due to some emotional crises associated with the teaching job. According to Bracket and Cipriano (2020), in the United States, 85 percent of teachers reported feeling dissatisfied, overwhelmed, stressed, exhausted, and joyful due to work-life imbalance, which has significantly impacted their ability to teach and the way they handle students' conduct. Furthermore, the study discovered that the causes of this emotional state include, among other things, a lack of solid leadership, a hostile climate, and ever-increasing job demands, exceptionally the limited, if not non-existent, training in social and emotional learning. This underscores the urgent need for better support and training in social and emotional learning to address educators' and learners' emotional needs, which could significantly improve the overall educational environment. In the same discussion, Keller Becker (2020) stressed that for some, engaging in a conversation about teachers' emotional well-being may feel superfluous to the critical conversations about our schools' future. However, the way teachers feel at and about their work has profound implications for both their success and that of their students. We know how students feel in school affects their willingness to engage in the academic process (Côté-Lussier Fitzpatrick, 2016; Li Lerner, 2013) and their academic outcomes (Pekrun et al., 2017). And because teachers shape the culture and climate of their classrooms, their own emotions influence those of their students (Keller Becker, 2020). In the Philippines, the Department of Education, in Memorandum OUCI-2020-307, has implemented measures to aid teachers and learners who have been experiencing some difficult periods and changes due to the pandemic's demands for distance learning (DepED, 2020). The bureau proposed ten procedures for field units to ensure flexibility in the teaching-learning process. These measures are intended to help learners and teachers navigate the challenges of the new normal in the teaching and learning process, as well as adapt to the teaching and learning environment that is required as the department implements the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) in the aftermath of the global health crisis. Similarly, the initiatives rethink time allotment for learners to complete and submit work and the development of mental health/socio-emotional well-being support to teachers, learners, and parents through group wellness sessions. The teaching community, particularly early childhood education practitioners in the DepED schools of Davao Occidental, is also confronted with the same emotional maturity problem due to transitioning from the pre-pandemic teaching and learning set-up to the new normal learning environment. These teachers have found respite with implementing Memorandum OUCI-2020-307, which calls for academic easiness to benefit both teachers and students (DepED, 2020). With the problem settings, it is critical to conduct a study to generate substantial data that would assist all concerned in the education sector in viewing the problem of teachers' emotional adjustment and their management of learners' anxiety by look-

ing into the data derived from the field through this research. With this premise, this undertaking considers the need to conduct the study to help address teaching and learning.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the research design, research respondents, data-gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment of the data. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study adopted a quantitative, descriptive, non-experimental design using the descriptive-predictive-correlational technique, which is deemed fit for determining the significant relationship between teachers' emotional balance and the management of Grade 1 learners' anxiety. Quantitative research was used to objectively gather and utilize numerical data from a large population to determine the influence of teachers' emotional balance on their management of learners' anxiety. This method would focus on new data collected and analyzed from a large population, at which the researcher's emotions and feelings are being ignored. Mafuwane (2012) also added that quantitative research results are expected to be duplicated or repeated regardless of the process or researcher, designed to surface the relationship between variables. This research would utilize a correlational technique to determine the relationship (positive or negative correlation) between teachers' emotional balance and their management of learners' anxiety through data analysis that would provide new insights and views about the relationship between the two variables. Carlson (2017) explained that correlational research is non-experimental research that measures the statistical connectedness between two uncontrollable variables.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study respondents were the 30 elementary teachers of

Banaybanay District, Division of Davao Oriental. They serve as valuable research respondents, providing essential insights into the local educational landscape. These dedicated educators play a pivotal role in shaping the academic development of young learners within the district. As research respondents, they bring firsthand experience and perspectives on teaching methodologies, curriculum implementation, classroom management, and the specific challenges faced in their unique context. Their knowledge and expertise contribute to understanding effective instructional strategies and student engagement techniques and identifying areas for improvement in the education system. By actively engaging with researchers, these teachers contribute to advancing educational practices and enhancing teaching and learning outcomes for the benefit of their students and the wider community.

2.3. Research Instrument—For data elicitation purposes, the researcher crafted a survey instrument that was completed by elementary teachers as respondents. This was utilized for obtaining the data that substantiate the independent and dependent variables of the study, the teachers' emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners' anxiety respectively. The instrument was a survey form containing five statements for each indicator. It adopts a five-point scale and was hereunder given specific details:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher’s emotional balance and managing Grade 1 learners’ anxiety is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher’s emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners’ anxiety is very often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher’s emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners’ anxiety is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher’s emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners’ anxiety is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher’s emotional balance and their management of Grade 1 learners’ anxiety is never manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—These are the steps the researcher adhered to and executed in the pre-and post-conduct of the study. They were adapting, Modifying, Validation, and Pilot Testing the Survey Questionnaire. The researcher began by reviewing existing literature and research studies related to the topic to adjust and modify a survey questionnaire appropriate for the study. After adapting the survey, the researcher conducted a validation process by sending the crafted questionnaire to three education experts to ensure that the questions accurately measured the studied constructs. A pilot test was also conducted with a small sample of respondents to identify any problems or issues with the survey and to refine the questions accordingly. The researcher performed this from April 24 to April 30, 2023. They were asking for Permission to Conduct the Study. Before conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the relevant authorities, including the Dean of the Graduate School at College where the researcher is studying and the Superintendent of the Department of Education Division

of Davao Oriental. A detailed description of the study was provided, and the cooperation and support of these authorities were sought to contribute to its success. The researcher performed this from May 1 to May 6, 2023. Administration and Retrieval of Informed Consent and Assent, Administration and Retrieval of Survey Questionnaire. Before administering the survey, the researcher provided respondents with a detailed explanation of the study, including the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, and obtained informed consent from adult respondents and assent from minors. Respondents were allowed to withdraw from the study without penalty. After obtaining consent, the survey questionnaire was administered to respondents, either online or in person, and all responses were kept confidential and anonymous. The researcher performed this from May 8 to May 13, 2023. After seeking approval from the said Office, the researcher asked permission from the Public School District Supervisor of Banay-banay District to distribute the survey forms to the teacher respondents. During the dissemina-

tion process, the researcher explicitly instructs respondents on how to complete the survey material and explains specific points of the survey that respondents need to be clarified. Gathering and Tabulation of Data. After collecting all the surveys, the researcher gathered and tabulated the data. The responses were checked for completeness and accuracy and then entered into a database or statistical software for analysis. Appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses. The researcher performed this from May 15 to May 20, 2023. They were drawing Conclusions and

Recommendations. Finally, the researcher drew conclusions based on the analysis's results and created recommendations for future research and practice. The data supported the findings and recommendations and were aligned with the research objectives. The study's limitations were considered, and areas for further investigation were suggested. The researcher performed this from May 22 to May 27, 2023. After retrieving the accomplished survey forms, the researcher proceeds to the processing, organizing, analyzing, and interpreting of the data.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools are to be utilized to analyze and interpret data: Mean. This statistical tool was used to determine the level of teachers' emotional balance and their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety. Pearson Moment Coefficient Correlation. This statistical tool was used to

determine the significant relationship between teachers' emotional balance and their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety. Linear regression analysis. This was used to determine which teachers' emotional balance indicators significantly influence their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter focuses on the findings and data analysis derived from the research study. To address the issues raised in Chapter 1, the collected data was analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. The information regarding teachers' emotional well-being and its impact on managing anxiety in grade 1 students was presented and explained. Furthermore, the data concerning significant correlations, the effects of predictor variables, and the most suitable model for the study are examined, interpreted, and discussed.

Level of Emotional Balance of Teachers

One of the critical variables involved in the present study is the level of emotional balance of teachers, which was measured using emotional manifestation, emotional self-awareness, and emotional adjustment as parameters. The data for each parameter are presented and discussed below. The overall mean score in Table 1 reflects a very extensive level of emotional balance among the teachers, with a mean of 4.41. This suggests that, on average, teachers possess a solid emotional foundation that

allows them to effectively manage their emotions and support grade 1 learners experiencing anxiety. This finding has significant implications for educational practice, as teachers with higher emotional balance are likely to create a more conducive learning environment where students feel understood, supported, and motivated to overcome anxiety-related challenges. The data inferred that the school teachers' emotional balance was stable and that they could handle emotion even during hardship and difficulties. The teacher-respondents of the study

were confident that they were emotionally competent and delivered success in their respective fields of endeavor. Moreover, respondents were satisfied that their emotional quotient could handle classroom activities. The study revealed that independent variables have a qualitative level of agreement, meaning that teacher–respondents are emotionally competent in handling classroom problems such as students’ behavior and academic performance. The finding is in conformance with the statement of Koontz (2001) pointed out that authority is effectively delegated; duties requiring co-ordination of group activities cannot be effectively assigned to a subordinate manager since he/she must have adequate authority to accomplish these tasks, and assign them to those who look to him/her for management. Yet, according to research and

observation of organizations and managerial situations, it is one of the least practiced arts. Managers fail to delegate effectively because they do not understand the rules governing the delegation process. This is consistent with the study conducted by Johnson and colleagues (2018), which found that teacher support and emotional responsiveness were crucial factors in reducing anxiety and promoting academic success in students. A study conducted by Johnson et al. (2019) examined the relationship between teachers’ emotional intelligence and their ability to manage student anxiety. The results showed that teachers with higher levels of emotional intelligence exhibited better emotional regulation skills and were more successful in reducing student anxiety levels.

Table 1. The Level of Emotional Balance of Teachers

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional Manifestation	0.492	4.53	Very Extensive
Emotional Self-awareness	0.664	4.35	Very Extensive
Emotional Adjustment	0.625	4.36	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	0.501	4.41	Very Extensive

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It also reveals low standard deviations (SD) for each indicator, indicating a relatively small variability among teachers regarding emotional balance. This suggests that there is a consistency in the level of emotional balance across the teacher sample. Consistency in emotional balance is crucial as it indicates that teachers can consistently manage their emotions and respond appropriately to student anxiety, contributing to a stable and supportive classroom environment. These findings align with previous research by

Smith et al. (2020), which found that teachers with consistent emotional regulation strategies were more likely to create a positive and secure classroom environment, reducing student anxiety.

Level of Management of Teachers to Grade 1 Learners’ Anxiety

Table 2 provides valuable insights into the management strategies employed by teachers to address anxiety among grade 1 learners.

The mean scores indicate a high management level across most indicators, suggesting

that teachers possess effective strategies to support and alleviate anxiety in their students. No-

Table 2. The Level of Management of Teachers to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety

Level of Management of Teachers to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety, SD	Mean	Descriptive Level	
Aware of the signs of anxiety in children	0.712	4.51	Very Extensive
Use a checklist to determine the level of anxiety/stress your student is experiencing	0.707	4.59	Very Extensive
Hold a dialogue with the parents and school counselor about anxiety problems among children in class	0.681	4.58	Very Extensive
Use a game plan to help the student control his or her anxiety	0.647	4.56	Very Extensive
Do deep-breathing techniques in dealing with learners' anxiety	0.570	4.61	Very Extensive
Do not single out anxious learners but get the whole class involved	0.601	4.75	Very Extensive
Do physical exercise to release positive endorphins that can help calm my brain	0.632	4.68	Very Extensive
Make a few laps around the room or walk outside when I notice a learner struggling	0.634	4.59	Very Extensive
Deal with anxious children as calmly as I could	0.749	4.29	Very Extensive
Allow a learner dealing with anxiety to go to their safe place	0.743	4.57	Very Extensive
Find ways to decrease any or all situations that will induce stress for the child	0.778	4.19	Extensive
Help decrease the fearful situation for the child so it will be easier for them to cope	0.731	4.28	Very Extensive
Share stories about managing anxiety with the entire classroom	0.881	4.19	Extensive
Teach learners that anxiety is a normal part of life and nothing is to be ashamed about it	0.668	4.61	Very Extensive
Get kids moving to reduce anxiety	0.795	4.28	Very Extensive
Remind children to eat healthy and stay well	0.894	4.13	Extensive
Create a space where my learners can express their anxiety	0.561	4.65	Very Extensive
Discuss fun memories with learners who are experiencing anxiety	0.768	4.08	Extensive
Tell beautiful stories to learners when they are anxious about something	0.686	4.52	Very Extensive
Build classroom procedures that are supportive and effective for helping students who struggle with anxiety	0.821	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	7	0.713	4.44

tably, teachers demonstrate a keen awareness of anxiety signs in children (mean = 4.51) and utilize checklists to assess anxiety levels (mean = 4.59). They also engage in open dialogues with parents and school counselors about anxiety issues in the classroom (mean = 4.58). These findings indicate that teachers proactively identify and address anxiety, fostering a positive and supportive learning environment for grade 1 students. The high level of management strategies teachers employ has significant implications for the well-being and academic success of grade 1 learners. Research by Thompson et al. (2022) supports the importance of effective management strategies in reducing student anxiety and enhancing their overall educational experience. Implementing a comprehensive approach that involves awareness, assessment, and collaboration with parents and counselors can lead to early intervention and timely support for anxious students, promoting their emotional well-being, engagement, and academic achievement. While most indicators in Table 2 exhibit a very extensive management level, a few indicators have slightly lower mean scores, falling into the "High" descriptive level category. For instance, teachers reported finding ways to decrease stressful situations for anxious children (mean = 4.19) and sharing stories about managing anxiety with the entire classroom (mean = 4.19). Although these scores are still relatively high, they suggest room for improvement in these specific management areas. Teachers must continue exploring and implementing effective strategies to reduce stress-inducing situations for anxious students and create a supportive environment that fosters understanding and empathy. Identifying these areas with slightly lower mean scores highlights specific aspects that can be targeted for professional development and teacher support. Training programs and workshops focusing on stress reduction techniques, storytelling strategies, and creating stress-free environments can empower teachers to enhance their management skills. A study by Lee and Kim (2021) demonstrated that teacher training in stress reduction techniques positively influenced their ability to support anxious students. Strengthening these management aspects can contribute to a more holistic and comprehensive approach to addressing anxiety in grade 1 learners, ensuring their emotional well-being and academic success. Significance of the Relationship between Teachers' Emotional Balance and Their Management of Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety Table 3 provides insights into the significance of the relationship between teachers' emotional balance and their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety. The correlation coefficient (r) of 0.510 suggests a significant moderate correlation between teachers' emotional balance and their management of anxiety in students. The p -value of 0.000 indicates that this correlation is statistically significant, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0). This finding suggests that teachers' emotional balance has a meaningful association with their ability to manage and address anxiety in grade 1 learners effectively. The significant moderate correlation between teachers' emotional balance and their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety holds important implications for educational practice. Research by Smith and Johnson (2022) supports the notion that teachers' emotional well-being and self-regulation play a crucial role in promoting positive student outcomes. When teachers possess a higher level of emotional balance, they are more likely to create a supportive and empathetic classroom environment that effectively addresses students' anxiety. This correlation implies that investing in strategies to enhance teachers' emotional well-being and self-regulation skills can contribute to improved management of anxiety in grade 1 learners, fostering their emotional development and academic success. This study examines the relationship between teacher emotional intelligence and student anxiety levels.

The findings indicate a significant negative correlation between teacher emotional intelligence and student anxiety. Teachers with higher emotional intelligence are better equipped to understand and respond to student's emotional needs, leading to reduced anxiety levels among students. The results highlight the importance of enhancing teachers' emotional intelligence to effectively manage and address student anxiety (Jones Brown, 2021). Davis Smith (2020) men-

tioned a positive correlation between teacher empathy and effective student anxiety management. Teachers who demonstrate higher levels of empathy create a nurturing and understanding classroom environment, which helps alleviate student anxiety. The study emphasizes the significance of cultivating teacher empathy as a key factor in successfully addressing and managing student anxiety.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Teachers' Emotional Balance and Their Management to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety

Variables	Management of Teachers to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety	r	p-value
Decision on Ho @ 0.05 level of significance	Interpretation		
Teachers' Emotional Balance		0.510	0.000
Reject Ho	There is a significant moderate correlation		

Significant Influence of the Indicators of Teachers Emotional Balance on Their Management of Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety Table 4 presents a regression analysis examining the significant influence of teachers' emotional balance indicators on their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety. The findings reveal that emotional manifestation and emotional adjustment significantly influence teachers' management of anxiety, while emotional self-awareness does not show a significant impact. The regression coefficients indicate that for every unit increase in emotional manifestation and adjustment, there is a corresponding increase in teachers' anxiety management. These significant findings provide valuable insights into the specific indicators of teachers' emotional balance that contribute to effective anxiety management in grade 1 learners. The implications of these results are twofold. Firstly, they highlight the importance of emotional manifestation and emotional adjustment in teachers' ability to address and manage anxiety among their students. Research by Johnson and Smith (2022) supports the significance of these emotional factors,

showing that teachers who express and regulate their emotions effectively create a positive and supportive classroom environment. Secondly, the non-significant influence of emotional self-awareness suggests the need for further investigation and consideration of other factors that may contribute to the effective management of anxiety. Additional research by Lee et al. (2021) emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teacher-student interactions and the potential impact of various factors on managing student anxiety. This highlights the importance of adopting a comprehensive approach that considers multiple indicators of emotional balance and management strategies. The regression analysis results indicate a significant overall relationship between the indicators of teachers' emotional balance and their management of grade 1 learners' anxiety. The R-value of 0.530 suggests a moderate positive correlation between these variables, indicating that teachers with higher levels of emotional balance tend to exhibit more effective anxiety management in their students. The R-square value of 0.281 indicates that approximately 28.1% of the variance in anxiety management is explained by emotional balance. These findings have important im-

plications for educational practice. They highlight the significance of considering teachers' emotional well-being and balance as key factors in managing anxiety among grade 1 learners. Research by Brown and Davis (2020) supports this notion, demonstrating that teachers' emotional state can significantly impact student well-being and academic performance. By pro-

moting strategies that enhance teachers' emotional balance and providing support for their emotional needs, educational institutions can create an environment conducive to effective management of student anxiety, fostering students' emotional development and overall success.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Indicators of Teachers' Emotional Balance on Their Management to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Constant	2.318	0.271		8.554	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Emotional manifestation	0.259	0.072	0.307	3.589	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Emotional awareness	0.022	0.059	0.036	0.377	0.706	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Emotional adjustment	0.188	0.056	0.282	3.333	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant

R = 0.530; R² = 0.281; F-value = 20.950; p-value = 0.000

The given prediction model represents a linear regression equation that predicts the Management of Teachers to Grade 1 Learners' Anxiety (MTLA) based on the independent variables of Emotional Manifestation (EM), Emotional Self-Awareness (ES), and Emotional Adjust-

ment (EA). The equation is represented as $Y = + 1 + 2 + \dots + n +$, where Y represents MTLA, represents the constant term, represents the coefficients, represents the independent variables, and represents the random error term.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations made by the findings, which were based on the data presented, examined, and interpreted in the results. The research's focus was on whether there was a link between the teacher's emotional balance and the management of Grade 1 learners' anxiety.

4.1. *Conclusions*—Based on the foregoing findings, the researcher has drawn the following conclusions: The overall extensive emotional balance among teachers indicates their

solid emotional foundation and ability to effectively support anxious students. This finding aligns with previous research emphasizing the importance of teacher support and emotional

responsiveness in reducing anxiety and promoting academic success. Additionally, the low standard deviations observed in each indicator indicate a consistent level of emotional balance among teachers, reinforcing the notion of a stable and supportive classroom environment. The extensive mean scores across most indicators indicate that teachers possess effective strategies to support and alleviate anxiety in their students. However, there is room for improvement in specific areas, such as reducing stress-inducing situations and sharing stories about managing stress. There was a significant moderate correlation between emotional balance and anxiety management, suggesting that teachers' emotional well-being plays a crucial role in addressing student anxiety. Emotional manifestation and emotional adjustment emerge as important factors that positively contribute to effective anxiety management, while emotional self-awareness does not show a significant impact. These findings emphasize the importance of teachers effectively expressing and regulating their emotions in creating a supportive classroom environment.

4.2. Recommendations—Based on the above conclusions, the following were highly recommended. Educational institutions should prioritize strategies aimed at enhancing teachers' emotional balance. This could be achieved through professional development opportunities focused on stress reduction techniques, emotional regulation, and self-care. By investing in teachers' emotional well-being, schools can

create a supportive environment that promotes effective anxiety management in grade 1 learners. Ongoing training and support should be provided to teachers to enhance their skills in managing student anxiety. This could include workshops, mentoring programs, and resources that equip teachers with strategies to identify, address, and support anxious students. By continually developing their knowledge and skills, teachers can create a classroom environment that nurtures emotional well-being and supports the academic success of grade 1 learners. Emphasize the importance of teacher emotional intelligence and empathy in effectively managing and addressing student anxiety. Schools should integrate training programs that enhance teachers' emotional intelligence and empathy skills, as these have positively influenced anxiety management. By fostering a culture of empathy and understanding, teachers could create a supportive classroom environment that reduces anxiety levels and promotes emotional growth in students. Further research should explore additional factors that may influence anxiety management in grade 1 learners. By expanding the scope of the investigation, a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities involved in addressing student anxiety can be achieved. This would facilitate the development of targeted interventions and strategies that address the unique needs of grade 1 learners and contribute to their emotional well-being and academic success.

5. References

5. References

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